

TRANSLATION PEDAGOGY (IES) IN MOROCCAN UNIVERSITIES: IS THERE ANY EFFECTIVE MEANS FOR USING THEORY IN THE UNDERGRADUATE TRANSLATION CURRICULA?

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The studies developed from within translation studies on the relevance of translation theory to translation practice are still of little significance and remain of no use in the undergraduate translation curricula. Accordingly, this paper departs from applied translation studies, as identified by James Holmes' map (Holmes, 1972), and contemporary translation pedagogies to highlight the necessity of interlinking translation theory to practice in teaching translation and to reflect on its "usefulness and usability" in-class practices (Rabadan, 2010, 9). In the light of the upcoming reform of Moroccan Universities, I believe that the implementation of the relevant theoretical component and its bridging with practice will achieve an interactive pedagogy in the undergraduate translation class and create an incentive environment of learning for the students so as to develop their translation skills. More importantly, by maintaining positive attitudes to translation theory professors will eventually encourage students to engage with the latest research in the field of translation studies and introduce them to new research models, which they can use for future MA and PhD studies.

Keywords: *Translation studies, applied translation studies, translation pedagogies, in-class strategies to develop the undergraduate students' understanding of translation theories as applied to their translation tasks.*

Introduction

This paper's object of study was inspired by both my experience in teaching Arabic-English-Arabic translation at the faculty of Letters in Mohamed V University in Rabat, and a recent attempt by its English department to start an MA program in translation and cultural studies. My experience in teaching translation to the undergraduate students of the English department *Initiation to Translation* (for S3) and Seminars about Translation Studies (For S5 and S6) is highly informed by my approach to this subject matter and my Colleagues' treatment of the same course. Throughout my coordination of the translation modules with the other colleagues, I have realized a striking disparity and divergence in the methods of teaching translation, which I believe is due to the different educational backgrounds of the Professors and their interpretation and understanding of the translation modules' descriptive templates.

The choice of this topic was equally inspired by a recent request from the English department of Mohamed V Faculty of Humanities to provide preliminary descriptive templates for the translation modules to be taught in the Master programme that will be launched next year. During the few meetings organized by the professors to discuss the content of the MA curricula, there were multiple questions to be answered. Questions about the place of translation theory should have in this programme: Does "Translation Studies" equal "Translation Theory for students of MA translation"? (And if not, what is the difference?) To what extent should the theoretical component be prescriptive, and 'what is the role of the descriptive approaches within it?' were also evoked. Unfortunately, just few colleagues could discuss these issues because the majority of the professors are not specialized in the field and probably because the need to answer these questions has never been considered seriously before. More importantly, in the English department of my

faculty, translation professors are at best merely interested in translation and have no former pedagogical training in the subject matter. This conclusion has been confirmed by the weak feedback I received to a questionnaire I shared with my colleagues in Rabat and with colleagues in other Moroccan Universities.

In the light of this, this paper departs from contemporary translation studies, namely applied translation studies as identified by Holmes, and the new translation pedagogies to highlight the necessity of interlinking translation theory to practice in teaching translation to the undergraduate students of English studies. Equally, this research attempts to demonstrate some strategies which I have myself undertaken in my undergraduate translation classes and in the translation seminars to my S5 and S6 students. On the one hand, by implementing these strategies at this level and by focusing more on the students' needs, I hope they will create a variety in the translation classes and develop incentive environments of learning for the students. On the other hand, by maintaining and by promoting positive attitudes to translation theory in the undergraduate translation classes, professors will eventually encourage students to engage with the latest research in the field of translation studies and the new research models which they can use either in their End Studies Projects, or in Future MA and PhD projects.

Research Methodology and Procedures

In this research, I have applied both qualitative and quantitative methods to demonstrate the necessity and the usefulness of Translation Studies (TS) and Applied Translation Studies (ATS) to improve the pedagogical tools used in teaching translation for the undergraduate students. The quantitative method has relied on the results of two different questionnaires: the first questionnaire was administered to translation professors in the faculty of Mohamed V and in other Moroccan faculties; the second questionnaire targeted mainly undergraduate students of S3, S5 and S6.

Empirically speaking, the Professors' questionnaire results cannot be reliable to come out with generalisations about translation didactics and all the teaching methods used for teaching translation in all Moroccan Universities, because the returned questionnaires amount to fifteen participants only. However, these questionnaires have reflected the non existence of an agreed upon teaching pedagogy of translation with clearly defined objectives at long and short terms. The participants' answers to the questionnaires and the description they provide for their course material and strategies remain far from what is stated in the course descriptions of the undergraduate modules: *Initiation to Translation* (S3), *Translation* (S4), and *Translation 1 & 2* for both the Linguistic and the Cultural Tracks of S5 & S6).

As to the qualitative method, it emphasizes the utility of contemporary translation studies and applied translation studies and their relevance to translation teaching pedagogies for the undergraduate students. The qualitative part of this research will also explain how these new translation pedagogies are applicable in the undergraduate translation classes in the light of my personal teaching experience at the faculty of Humanities of Mohamed V University in Rabat.

The significance of the Study

This research is based on the experience I gained in the department of English Studies while teaching and coordinating the S3 module of *Initiation to Translation* in Arabic-English-Arabic translation. Although this research is connected to a specific teaching/learning experience and draws on data collected from questionnaires, the results and the tensions characterizing both the professors' and students' responses are indicative of two strikingly reversed attitudes. While there

is a general agreement among the professors to focus more on translation practice and discard theoretical issues in-class, the students expressed their need and willingness to discuss them.

Equally important, this research can be considered as a 'reflective practice' in which I explore the significance of doing translation by using a theory of doing translation [1]. In this respect, Farghal states that reflecting on human experience and working with it is very important in learning [2, p.5-7]. Similarly, Teo Hermans defines reflections on self-experiences in teaching translation as non negligible parts of translation studies as they can explain and explore "[t]he ways in which translation is both practised and theorized in individual cultures" [Hermans, 2002, as cited in Galazda, 2005]. Practice and theories do not exist on their own; they are interdependent on one another. In Hermans' words, "we necessarily translate according to our concept of translation, and into our concept of translation". As far as the complementarity between the practice of translation and theory of translation is concerned, Basil Hatim calls into question the distinction between theory and practice in translation teaching: Activities such as translating or translation teaching have, until fairly recently, been kept separate from 'research' into these and related issues. The polarisation is historical and is evidence of the misleading demarcation lines that are often too readily drawn between 'theoretician' and 'practitioner' in many disciplines. Theory and practice are ultimately complementary and, particularly in a field such as translation, the distinction needs to be re-examined [1, p.3].

In similar vein, Fargahali explains that for translation courses to build their own legitimate reality, translation instructors have to recognize the importance of translation theory. According to him, translation competence alone is not sufficient for those who are involved in teaching translation (i.e. a theory of translating) is all that is needed for the teaching of translation courses just as language competence alone (i.e. a theory of communicating) is far from being sufficient for teaching language courses. As matter of fact, Farghal recommends that a theory of translation is indispensable and that it is not even enough when it comes to giving formal instruction in translation classes [2, p.13].

The role of translation theory is intended to refine and sharpen the already existing level of translating theory by bringing to consciousness a set of strategies and principles in practicing and/or prospective translators. In this case, the practicing/prospective translator is expected to work with many theoretical options whose practical application manifests itself in a translational decision, which is, in the presence of a theory of translation, both practically and theoretically motivated.

Departing from this premise, this paper contends that the use of contemporary translation studies to improve the pedagogies and methods of teaching translation for the undergraduate students will ultimately trigger students' motivations and enhance their skill in doing translation tasks, which will enable them to apply for Master programmes in translation or think of a future career in translation. Moreover, the implementation of the Bachelor system in Moroccan Universities aims at improving student's competences and soft skills so that they can integrate the professional environment successfully. In the light of the existing methods and curricula of teaching translation, I doubt it will be possible, both at short and long terms, to attain those objectives, especially what concerns the improvement of soft skills which include critical thinking and problem solving as major strategies of learning. Ahmed Alaoui, a professional translator and a former professor of translation in the faculty of Rabat had considered the conditions of translation teaching in the faculty and pointed out that: The lack of clarity of the translation course objectives is a corollary of a wider sphere of fuzziness that characterizes university studies in Morocco. The recent university Reform has been initiated so as to produce graduates with marketable skills; however,

course objectives, trainers, teaching methods, teaching materials, staff recruitment policy, teaching aids and student enrolment policy clearly indicate that we are still flogging the same dead horse. Virtually all English departments course descriptions state that the aim of the course is to introduce students to translation theory and train them to translate from Arabic into English and vice versa [4].

Last and not least, although important Master programmes are offered by Moroccan Universities and many PhD dissertations about the practice of translation and translation studies are conducted in the English Departments of Moroccan Universities, these fields are still dealt with as either a purely linguistic research areas or as a field of comparative literature. Except for some leading faculties of humanities which have included cultural and postcolonial translation studies in their MA and PhD programmes, an important literature about contemporary Translation Studies, including Applied Translation Studies, remains unexplored.

I. The Quantitative Study: Procedure and Material

The results of this study are based on the feedback I received to two main questionnaires. While the first questionnaire targeted my colleagues in the English department of Mohamed V faculty of humanities and Professors in other Moroccan Universities, the second one was administered to my undergraduate students in S3, S5, and S6. Both questionnaires were prepared as google form documents in order to facilitate their accessibility by the targeted participants.

1. Discussion of Professors' Answers to the Questionnaire

The responses I received to the questionnaire which targeted my colleagues in the English Department of Mohamed V faculty of Humanities were very few, amounting to only 5 participants out of 38. It is true that this attitude on the part of my colleagues is indicative of the little importance given to translation in comparison to the other programmed modules, but the primary results of the returned questionnaires would be of little input to a study about the relevance and application of translation studies to the teaching and curricula design. Therefore, the solution was to widen the sphere of the targeted participants by including colleagues from other Moroccan Universities, which proved to be very fruitful indeed. In addition to Cadi Ayyad faculty of humanities in the University of Marrakesh, Chooab Dokkali in Eljadida, and Mohamed First in Oujda, I also shared the questionnaire with professors at King Fahd School of Translation in Tangier. The latter offers translation training MA programs for vocational purposes.

To collect the necessary research data, the requested information in the professor's questionnaire focused on:

- ✓ The Years of experience in teaching translation;
- ✓ The languages used in the translation course;
- ✓ The type of translation which is taught: General and/or Specialized, including literary translation;
- ✓ The pedagogy/ strategies/tools used for the course design and the choice of teaching materials;
- ✓ The necessity of using some theoretical foregrounding before assigning translation tasks to the students;
- ✓ Whether students' translation skills have to be dependent of practice only or of both practice and theory.

The analysis of the Professors' answers revealed the following results:

Experience in teaching translation	It varies from one year, six years, nine years to sixteen years.
Languages used for translation practice	Arabic and English are the main languages. French is sometimes used for the international students who are not able to translate from Arabic. French is considered as an important language variety in King Fahd School of Translation.
Types of translation taught	General translation is the major type of translation taught for the undergraduate students in Mohamed V University. Professors from Qadi Ayyad and Chouab Doukkali Universities affirmed teaching both general and specialized translation, including literary translation.
Pedagogy, Course design, and teaching material	Almost all the Professors relied on using handouts with short tasks for the students of <i>Initiation to Translation</i> , and longer passages and texts for the higher levels, usually done in accordance with the students' language proficiency. The course is realized in two main phases: First, the students are asked to do the translation in class; second, students take turn to read their translation products while the Professor comments on them and give his/her final appropriate answer.
Practice only or theory and practice to improve Students' translation skills?	Some Professors emphasized the importance of relevant theoretical contents for the course designs, but added that theoretical issues are usually tackled while correcting the students' translation products. Others, however, agreed on the importance of some theories in explaining translation strategies. Professors from Chouab Doukkali's University emphasized the importance of introducing theory to the MA students, while practice should be the only means for teaching translation for the undergraduate students.

Interestingly, in response to a question inquiring about the professors' remarks and recommendations to improve the quality of translation courses, eight out of the ten professors who provided their answers agreed that teaching translation should be assigned to professors who are specialized in the subject. Others recommended that, in addition to the focus on translation theory,

translation tools and softwares have to be available to the students in order to provide them with the maximum level of professionalism in the field.

II. The Students' Questionnaire Results

The aim of addressing a questionnaire to undergraduate students (semesters S3 and S5-S6) was twofolds, to confirm the idea that the majority of the students received in class instructions about translation practice only, and to test their acceptance or refusal of the theoretical content. Despite the low return rate at which students sent their answers, fifty-eight questionnaires were collected on an entirely voluntary basis and suggested that the participants well preceived the content of the questionnaire and their answers proved that it addressed an important issue to the students.

<p>The level of study of the participant students.</p>	<p>86% of the participants were mainly the undergraduate students of the English department of Mohamed V University.</p> <p>The other participants were the Master students of the English Department of King Fahd School of translation in Tangier.</p>
<p>The types of translation course which students took at their instutions.</p>	<p>Genral Arabic-English-Arabic translation represents 90% of the undergraduate translation courses at Mohamed V University.</p> <p>Fahd school students are trained in both general and specialized translation.</p>
<p>The Professors' method/strategy to teach translation.</p>	<p>70% of the undergraduate students at Mohamed V university said that the method deployed in translation classes relied on the immediate presentation of the task to be done and the professors' quick feedback as soon as they finish it.</p> <p>Only 19% of the participants confirmed having been exposed to a particular issue or problematic in translation with a relevant theoretical foregrounding before starting their tasks.</p> <p>The other participants stated that their professors explained particular translation problems while they corrected the translation tasks, but no relevant theoretical input was used to that regard.</p>
<p>The students' evaluation of their performance when Professors provide them with relevant theoretical foregrounding for the translation tasks.</p>	<p>More than 72% of the participants said that they understand the tasks better when these latters are foregrounded theoretically; whereas only 15% of them said the contrary.</p>

<p>The students' opinion about the means to improve their translation skills: by practice only or by both practice and theory?</p>	<p>7% of the students said by practice only. 20% of the students said by practice and a general theory of translation. 73 % of the participants agreed on the importance of practice and the use of relevant theoretical explanation of some translation problems.</p>
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Clearly, the students' feedback confirmed their need for practical tasks that are preceded by relevant theoretical explanations, showing them how to proceed with translating. More importantly, some students stated that the theories of translation will change their attitude towards the practice. Other undergraduate students expressed their frustration, because they haven't been taught specialized translation. These answers confirm *that General Translation* and its practice are the focus of the translation classes in the English department in the Faculty of Humanities of Mohamed University.

Taking into consideration these important results, the next section of the research will attempt to demonstrate the importance of contemporary translation studies, applied translation studies in particular, and their relevance to translation teaching for undergraduate students. The last section of the research will shed light on my own deployment of these theories in my translation classes as an answer to the question: Is there any effective means for using theory in the undergraduate translation curricula of the English department?

III. Translation Studies and its Contribution to Translation Teaching

Although Translation Studies has become an interesting field of research in Moroccan Universities and among Moroccan academia, criticism is still being directed to theories of translation and their irrelevance to real translation practices. What is really unconceivable is the fact that these negative attitudes are sometimes expressed by professional translators and interpreters. The latter think that translation studies are of no real or immediate use to translating, which they believe is a craft that relies on linguistic competence only and language proficiency in both the source and the target languages. Translation Studies is, therefore, challenged by translation practitioners because of, according to them, its irrelevance and ineffectiveness to translation teaching and translation training.

In this respect, Jeremy Munday explains that the study of translation as an academic subject has started recently and that it began in the past sixty years in the English-speaking world. This discipline is now generally known as 'Translation Studies', thanks to the Dutch-based US scholar James Holmes. Munday summerizes the main reasons behind the hostile attitude toward Translation Studies as follows:

Translation Studies is the discipline which studies phenomena associated with translating in its many and different forms. TS is a relatively new area of inquiry dating from the second half of the twentieth century and initially emerging out from other fields such as Modern languages, comparative literature and linguistics. Like other new areas of study, it has had to fight for recognition and was additionally hampered by an entrenched bias against it resulting from a long-held disregard for translation [5, p.9].

In addition to the fact that the majority of translation professors in Moroccan Universities are not specialized in the field of translation and translation studies, Munday's point of view may also explain why contemporary translation studies are still of little use in translation curricula of the English department in our Moroccan Universities.

1. Holmes' Translation Studies Map

James Holmes's paper: *'The Name and Nature of Translation Studies'* is generally accepted as the founding statement for a general and inclusive theory of translation that will "serve to explain and predict all phenomena falling within the terrain of translating and translation." [6, p.176-177]. Holmes's seminal paper, which he gave in the translation section of the "Third International Congress of Applied Linguistics" held in Copenhagen in August 1972, was designed as the « map » of an "empirical" "disciplinary utopia". In Holmes' own words, it is "a new sense of a shared interest in a common set of problems, approaches, and objectives on the part of a new grouping of researchers." [Ibid, p.182-183]. According to Mary Snell Hornby, Holmes' paper formulated the "raw program" and presented "the manifesto" to today's discipline...but from today's viewpoint, and rises a visionary blue print of the future discipline." [7, p.40-41].

Holmes breaks Translation Studies down into three areas of focus: (1) *the descriptive branch*: to describe phenomena of translations as they manifest themselves in the world of our experience; (2) *the theory branch*: to establish principles by which these phenomena can be explained and predicted; (3) *the applied branch*: to use information gained from 1 and 2 in the practice of translation and training of translators. While Holmes presents the three distinct branches of the discipline, descriptive, theoretical and applied, he insists on their relationship as complementary and dialectical:

The relation is a dialectical one, with each of the three branches supplying materials for the other two, and making use of the findings which they in turn provide. Translation theory, for instance, cannot do without the solid, specific data yielded by research in descriptive and applied translation studies, while on the other hand one cannot even begin to work [6].

The applied branch, as defined by Holmes and explained by Gideon Toury, includes:

- ✓ *Translator training*: teaching methods, testing techniques, curriculum design;
- ✓ *Translation aids*: such as dictionaries, grammars and information technology;
- ✓ *Translation criticism*: the evaluation of translations, including the marking of students' translations and the reviews of published translations [8, p.9-10].

Toury's revision of James Holmes' map of Translation Studies [9, p.7] maintained the same disciplinary division, but named the applied branch as "applied extensions". Toury referred to these extensions as the *bridging rules* between the findings of translation studies and their actual applications. (Ibid) Moreover, Daniel Gile explains that Holmes' map has included a large component devoted to applications, and that "considerable volume of Translation Studies literature is devoted to real-world problems related to training, to quality, to issues in legal translation, in medical translation, to the professional status and working environment of translators and interpreters." [10, p.11].

2. The Usefulness and Usability of Applied Translation Studies

Rosa Rabadan defines Applied Translation Studies as: the performative branch of Translation Studies (TS), which is concerned with translation activities that address a particular goal and a

specific (group of) final user(s) and that imply doing something with, for or about translation according to some standard of quality. ATS designates fields which partly belong in TS and partly in other disciplines such as translator training/education), translation tools [9, p.7].

Rabadan redefines the applied branch of translation studies in terms of their usability and usefulness to both academic researchers and professionals who expect to be supplied with reliable and applicable data. While usefulness concerns the relevance of the findings for the task at hand and the extent to which the application helps users to solve their problems, usability aims at bridging the gap between application and intended users [9, p.8].

Indeed, contemporary applied translation studies have recently proved their relevance to translation pedagogy and have produced non-negligible researches about the usability and usefulness of translation theory to teaching translation, which has definitely influenced translators' training and translation teaching. According to Basil Hatim, applied translation studies have been characterized by the immergence of a rich research literature on how the new theories of translation could be used and integrated in translation teaching. Hatim calls for the reassessment of the dichotomy between theory and practice and be replaced by a recognition of the dialectical relationship between 'research' and 'action'. Moreover, Hatim highlights the role of translation teachers in the identification of interesting problem areas and research aimed at providing answers to a range of practical questions and strategies to deal with problems emerging in the real time process of translation teaching [1, p.3-7].

In the light of this argument, I highly believe that there is an urgent need to consider the findings of these studies by Moroccan University Professors of translation in order to adapt them to the undergraduate translation classes. Interestingly, the descriptive templates of the translation modules of S3, S4, S5 and S6 provide the guidelines of an integrative approach to how translation should be taught to the undergraduate students. Among the objectives of the translation modules, there is an emphasis on improving translation skills of the students in the practice of Arabic-English-Arabic translation and helping them to grasp the translation jargon and special terminology pertaining to translation theory in order to:

1. Introduce students to the basic skills and strategies of translation from English into Arabic and vice versa;
2. Help them master the basic terminology and have an understanding of the fundamental notions pertaining to the translation activity (definition of translation, parties involved in the translation process, source vs. target texts, message transfer and interpretation, etc.);
3. Help them understand and apply the main stages of the translation process;
4. Enable them to acquire the necessary know-how for detecting and addressing translation linguistic and cultural problems when dealing with a variety of text types.
5. Raise their awareness of cross-cultural issues and the impact of cultural differences on the translation process;
6. Help them develop critical thinking towards the content and quality of texts and their evaluation by confronting the source and the target texts;
7. Develop their reading and writing skills, and enhance their mastery of both the source and the target languages;
8. Help them to use dictionaries effectively with a translation intention.

Another scrutinized reading in the description of *Translation 2* module, both for the linguistic and cultural tracks, reflects more ambitious goals such as introducing students to specialized translation activities (Translating Legal documents, international agreements, and some

Literary texts' extracts), and encourage them to do some critical readings of the translation products. However, these idealized and well integrated curricula of translation remains just "ink on paper". The coordination meetings of the translation professors, which I attended in the English department during the last three years, unravelled a lack of a common pedagogy and methods of teaching translation. I could understand better this situation after I had access to the material taught for the undergraduate students, which my colleagues in the department shared with their students through a common platform that the faculty of humanities of Mohamed V University has made available during the pandemic situation.

After comparing the methods and the material deployed for the translation classes, I can almost confirm that the existing translation teaching method focuses more on the translation product of the students and generally invites them to study the linguistic aspects of the source Arabic text and compare it to the final translated English text using a contrastive analysis of both languages' structures. Undeniably, no one can undermine the importance of this approach to translation practice especially in the initiation stage; but if we take into consideration the modules' objectives this method remains of little output and insufficient to their achievement. So, the last section of this study will tackle my exploration of Holmes map of Translation Studies and Applied Translation Studies so as to adapt them to my translation course design.

IV. In-class strategies to develop undergraduate students' understanding of translation theories as applied to their translation tasks

The classical method of translation Professors consists of students' learning to translate after an unguided and quick reading of the text to be translated. Then, usually the students' translations products are evaluated and judged to be "*false*" or "*correct*" in the light of the professor's already prepared translation of the same text. The following quote of Juliane House offers an excellent description of a typical translation class from the early days of translation courses at European Universities.

The teacher of the course, a native speaker of the target language, passes out a text (the reason for the selection of this text is usually not explained, because it is often a literary essay that the teacher has just "found" by accident). The text is full of traps, which means that the teachers do not set out to train students in the complex and difficult art of translation, but to ensnare them and lead them into error. The text is then prepared, either orally or in written form, for the following sessions and then the whole group goes through the text sentence by sentence, with each sentence being read by a different student. The instructor asks for alternative translation solutions, corrects the suggested versions and finally presents the sentence in its final, "correct" form. This procedure is naturally very frustrating for the students [11, p. 389].

Unfortunately, this pedagogy of teaching translation, wherein interaction in the translation classroom is based on comparing students' translation product to the Professor's translated version, is far from achieving any actual learning of techniques that students may use in future translation tasks. One major cause of this situation as explained by Dorothy Kelly is that translation teaching has been widely used as part of foreign language teaching programmes. The participant professors to this study have already agreed on the fact that the real constraint for implementing new methods of teaching translation is that many of the undergraduate students, as well as students admitted to specialized translation programs do not possess the adequate language competence in the target language, predominantly English, let alone in the source language which is Arabic. The Professors' design of the translation course and the choice of the material have one major objective:

to test students' ability in using English as the foreign language being learnt, while Arabic is used for the comprehension of their basically Arabic texts. This might explain why most translation courses at Moroccan Universities turn into language teaching rather translation courses proper which teaches translation as a skill in its own right [12, p.186].

While it is true that translation practice is a sophisticated linguistic exercise that calls for particular level of knowledge in the source and target languages, using translation in language learning and acquisition has been a controversial subject in translation studies and language pedagogy. Experts in language pedagogy have seriously dismissed the translation as a fruitful method of learning [12, p.185]. Similarly, Munday argues that the object of study has been reconsidered and shifted from translation as primarily connected to language teaching and learning to the specific study of what happens in and around translation, translating and translators [8, p.15].

In what follows, I attempt to explain my method of teaching translation and the concepts and strategies at work as I borrow them from Applied Translation Studies to be used in my undergraduate translation classes. My approach questions and reconsiders the practicality of the contrastive linguistics approach in improving student's performance in translating. It highlights that translation is a complex activity which should be considered as a process that involves, in addition to language comprehension, problem solving techniques and critical attitudes to the translation products.

1) Process Versus Product Oriented Method

My short experience with the undergraduate students of the English Department in S3, S5 and S6 has helped me to understand that what really matters for the students' motivations during the translation activity is not the different theories of translation I can introduce to them, but rather the grasping of the concepts these translation theories provide for understanding the translation activity and the different methods one can use, while learning how and why they are applicable. Emphasizing the knowledge of *how* and *why* a particular method of translation is used and even the bias behind using it will trigger students' interest and motivation to do the practice. Although it would be challenging to expose students at this level of studies to many theories of translation, it would be very helpful at first to explain to them that translating from Arabic to English and vice versa is more interesting than a mere literal rendering or a word for word equivalence between these two different languages. Students' attention should therefore be drawn to focus more on the translating process and the different steps they can undertake to achieve the translation task. I believe that the *process-oriented* approach has proved its utility and its efficiency in teaching translation better than the *product-oriented* approach.

The process-oriented approach conceives of translating as a multi-faceted activity, and calls for the use of variety of perspectives and tools in dealing with the translation task. This approach, moreover, supports an interactive environment in class, while it boosts students' understanding of translating strategies. Students are, therefore, considered as learners of different translation methods, strategies, and tools rather than as producers of finished products; and are pushed to inquire about the use of a particular method for a particular purpose. Students are also able to understand that there is more than one viable target text and their translation products are seen as non final products, which they could revise and correct themselves. For this purpose, translation needs to be viewed as an act of communication governed by considerations of comprehension and interpretation, rather than an act of prescription informed by obsolete views about correctness. In this respect, Daniel Gile adds "the process-oriented approach indicates to the student good translation principles, methods, and procedures." [11, p.390].

As I noticed in my own translation classes, the process oriented approach is very useful for the early stages of learning and doing translation. This approach seeks to increase students' awareness and confidence in using a variety of translating strategies from which they will eventually choose the most appropriate one at a particular time and place and under given circumstances. So, in addition to the linguistic competence necessary for the comprehension of the source text and the production of the target text, students can improve their translation competences and skills by identifying the series of decision making and selecting processes and problem solving involved in the translation task.

On another level, dealing with the translation activity as a complex cognitive process entails the design of some clearly defined objectives and goals, usually announced to the students before starting the lesson. The formulation of objectives offers the following advantages as summarized by Delisle:

1. Facilitates communication between teachers and students
2. Facilitates the choice of teaching tools
3. Suggests different learning activities
4. It provides a basis from which to assess learning [11, p.390].

To achieve the course objectives of my translation class, a series of strategies and steps to be followed are explained to the students to facilitate and orient their translation tasks among which I can cite the following:

✓ **The pre-translating strategies** which include the reading, the comprehension and the analysis of a passage, a text or a segment of a text to be translated. At this preliminary stage, students' communicative competences are emphasized through the identification of ideas, facts, phenomena, which are discussed in relation to real life situations/issues.

✓ **The organizing strategies**, which consist of identifying the different sections, segments, and units of meaning in the text by considering its cohesion and coherence;

✓ **The searching strategies**, during which students look for special vocabulary, terminology, difficult lexicon and their indexation in a glossary to be checked out in an English or Arabic monolingual dictionary and if necessary in a bilingual dictionary;

✓ **The production strategies**, which consist of a process of transfer and switching between Arabic and English or vice versa writing up a primary draft of the target text, solving local problems. At this stage, emphasis is on translating strategies and methods in order to improve students' ability to identify a particular translation problem, understand the constraints and options of problem resolutions, and understand the different viewpoints which inform decision-making to resolve a given problem [1, p.195-196].

✓ **The Revision strategies** during which both the students and the professor discuss the translation products in order to achieve a more appropriate final version. At this time students are encouraged to revise their own translation products and improve them.

Concerning the in-class feedbacks, professors should show more flexibility to accept students' solutions so as to avoid their demotivation, especially during the early stages of learning translation. For this purpose, professors are also advised to invent entirely new methods of assessment and error correction in order to reach the desired pedagogical goal.

To sum up, the translation course involves three main stages: "The pre-translating, the translating and the re-translating stages" [2, p.9]. In addition to its usability in the organization of the translation task, the process-oriented approach enhances the act of communication and the communicative competences of the students, and favours a dynamic participation in the translation

activity. Equally important, focusing on the translation process instead of the product helps the students to accumulate experience in problem solving by using particular strategies and tactics.

2) Translation Strategies and Problem Solving

Usually, the first element I explain during my translation sessions is that strategy is not constitutive element for a general theory of translation, but rather a tool to tackle the possible problems that emerge during the translation process. Translation strategies, as Gambier explains: “are not prescriptive (what are the strategies for translating so and so? Rather than descriptive How so and so has been translated or is translated in a given, real situation.” [13, p.414]. The purpose is, therefore, to explain that these strategies are not used in a prescriptive and controlled way, but should be adapted to the students’ needs and to the nature of the problem to be solved. Moreover, students have to be put in different translational situations in order to be able to identify as many as possible of translation problems and their solutions.

Generally, the problems encountered by students when doing a translation task can be identified in several ways and at different levels: linguistic, textual, extralinguistic, and cultural. These different levels vary in scope and importance depending on the targeted groups of students and their undergraduate level. In the following I summarize how this translation teaching pedagogy is achieved for my S3, S5 and S6 classes.

During the initiating sessions of translation practice, the course design and the choice of the material for Arabic-English-Arabic translation tasks focus more on a contrastive analysis that highlights the linguistic differences between the two languages; (at this level students may understand the inefficiency of a word for word and literal translation). Different methods of translation can be introduced later on to explain their usefulness and usability in the process of translation: Literal, faithful; communicative; free or idiomatizing. The translation exercises and practices are accordingly designed efficiently and effectively so that the students use one of these methods.

In the final learning stages, I maximize the use of longer texts based on particular communicative contents and functions. This pedagogy exposes students to more complex translation tasks and introduces them to specific concepts such as: text types/genres, purpose/scopus, discourse, cohesion and coherence. At this level, I can either make use of some simple informative/ expository texts; or more technical texts to explain some professional uses of translation and the existence of other specialized fields of translation.

This higher level of instruction in translation is intensified for my End Studies Project supervisees of S5 and S6. The course is primarily designed to meet the students’ needs for grasping research methodology, theoretical frameworks and concepts to be used in a research paper about translation practices. The seminars’ input is based on the recent translation studies and helps the students to explore a variety of interdisciplinary approaches to translation. Students are more aware of the translators’ bias and ethics in translating and are guided to understand them through a critical reading of some Moroccan literary Arabic texts in English translations.

It is evident that students at this level of studies will not be able to understand all the philosophical, socio-cultural and the ideological dynamics underpinning literary translation, but they are at least acquainted with some concepts which they can eventually identify and use in future specialized training programmes or MA programmes after they finish the undergraduate level. My ultimate objective is that the students combat their fear to explore this field of research.

Conclusion

In this paper, I have argued that while it is difficult to quantify its scientific contribution to translation practice, Translation Studies, namely the applied branch, is a real aid for University translation professors. I have attempted to give ample evidence to show the usability and usefulness of these studies for the improvement of translation pedagogies in Moroccan Universities. Taking into consideration the challenges posed by the upcoming Bachelor reform, these kind of studies will, no doubt, help professors to capture the essence and the significance of in-class translation activities and enrich students' adequate knowledge and understanding of the translation techniques and concepts by which they can orient themselves in future professional careers in translation practice or researches on translation.

Last but not least, based on the findings of the study at hand, I believe that Moroccan University professors of translation and academic researchers are highly responsible for boosting in-class pedagogical innovations aiming at the improvement of the outcomes of the educational process. Thus, the application of new methods, techniques, tools, new concepts, new textbooks, and new curricula has become an imperative. The teaching methods and the new trends in translation pedagogies have recently developed more innovative tools in teaching translation, namely specialized translation. A variety of hardware and software programmes, and virtual classes and international telecollaboration projects are increasingly adopted. The present pandemic situation has even called for an intensive use of these tools to ensure the continuity and the good quality of the teaching and learning processes.

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